

POSE-GUIDED MULTI-PART ATTENTION FRAMEWORK FOR VIDEO-BASED PERSON REIDENTIFICATION

RANA. S.M. SAAD^{1, *}, MONA. M. MOUSSA¹, NEMAT S. ABDELKADER², HESHAM FAROUK¹

¹Computer And Systems Department, Electronics Research Institute, Cairo, Egypt.

²Electronics And Electrical Communications Engineering, Cairo University, Egypt.

E-mail: ¹rana@eri.sci.eg, ¹mona_moussa@eri.sci.eg, ²neamt2000@hotmail.com, ¹hesham@eri.sci.eg

ABSTRACT

Person Re-Identification (ReID) is a fundamental task in intelligent video surveillance, aiming to recognize individuals across non-overlapping camera views. Despite significant progress, video-based ReID remains challenging due to variations in illumination, occlusion, and dynamic background clutter. To address these challenges, we present a novel ReID framework that jointly exploits spatial and temporal cues for robust person retrieval. The proposed approach integrates multi-level spatial representations by combining global, intermediate, and fine-grained features. Global and intermediate information is captured through self-attention mechanism, while fine-grained details are derived from pose-based attributes to enhance discriminative power. These spatial representations are then fused and processed by a temporal self-attention module, which models inter-frame dependencies to effectively capture motion dynamics. A retrieval stage subsequently leverages the joint spatial-temporal features to achieve accurate identification. Comprehensive experiments on the PRID2011 and iLIDS-VID benchmark datasets demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed method. The framework achieves consistent improvements over baseline approaches, with gains of 2.3% and 3.4% in mean Average Precision (mAP) on PRID2011 and iLIDS-VID, respectively. These results highlight the robustness and discriminative capability of the proposed architecture for real-world video-based ReID applications.

Keywords: *Video Person Re-Identification; Person Re-Identification; Heatmaps; Pose; Pose Detection; Video Surveillance.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Person Re-identification (ReID) entails the recognition of individuals across disparate, non-overlapping camera viewpoints. Over the past decade, person ReID has attracted significant attention due to its critical role in surveillance applications, security monitoring, criminal investigations, forensic analysis, and the identification of missing individuals in crowded environments such as shopping malls [1]. However, the widespread use of surveillance cameras renders human re-identification a considerable difficulty. Various factors pose a challenge, including discrepancies in an individual's appearance due to variations in posture, illumination, and low resolution. Additionally, external factors such as occlusion, background clutter, and bounding box misalignment further complicate the re-identification process [2-4].

Video-ReID has recently emerged as an effective approach by leveraging rich temporal information to enhance re-identification accuracy [5-6]. On the

other hand, the temporal data poses computational challenges, negatively impacting system performance and runtime efficiency. A wide range of Video-ReID approaches have been developed to enhance Video-ReID effectiveness [7-10]. The methods focus on utilizing several spatial and temporal feature extraction techniques to enhance retrieval outcomes. State of the art Video-ReID methodologies predominantly rely on attention mechanisms [11, 12], graph-based frameworks [13, 14], and transformer-based structures [15, 16]. Nevertheless, the performance of various approaches remains comparable on benchmark datasets.

Despite the deployment of these approaches, the variability of datasets across different environments presents challenges such as occlusion by other individuals or objects, whether totally or partially. Additionally, partial occlusion may vary in severity, ranging from significant to minimal, compounded by lighting variability and the presence of multiple individuals in frames, all of which hinder the

approach's ability to achieve superior results. Figure 1 illustrates the difference between hard and mild occlusion.

Figure 1: Various Occlusion Pattern

This paper introduces a framework that extracts spatial and temporal features. The spatial frame features comprise three separate levels: Global Appearance Features (GAF), Moderate Part-attention Features (MPF), and Fine-grained Pose-guided Features (FPF). GAF obtains the global feature for the whole input frame. MPF are obtained employing dual granularity self-attention mechanism, while the FPF are derived from a pose estimation technique [19]. The combination of these three spatial feature levels is transmitted to the Temporal Part-attention Module (TPM). Experiments demonstrate that the proposed methodology outperforms recent state-of-the-art techniques on benchmark datasets, highlighting its robustness. This paper's key contributions are as follows:

- Proposing a unified framework that fuses global, intermediate, and fine-grained representations to construct a more comprehensive and robust spatial feature representation for each video frame.

- Introducing pose heatmaps as fine-grained features for video-based person ReID, leveraging their intensity distributions as discriminative spatial features that directly associated with individual identities.

- Integrating a multipart self-attention mechanism in dual granular spatial representation with the temporal formulation to effectively models dependencies across consecutive frames, thereby achieving a favorable balance between accuracy and complexity.

- Conducting extensive evaluations on multiple benchmark datasets, demonstrating that the proposed framework consistently outperforms recent state-of-the-art methods and validates its robustness and generalization capability.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a review of the related work. Section 3 presents the proposed system in details. Section 4 discusses the experimental results and the datasets used for evaluation. Finally, Section 5 includes the ablation study and concludes the paper.

2. RELATED WORK:

2.1 Video ReID:

In literature, some Video-ReID systems concentrate on addressing the reidentification challenges such as handling open environment issues [20], cloth-changing problem [21]; while other approaches address spatial, temporal, and spatiotemporal feature learning for a feature representation perspective [1]. The study of temporal elements forms a key aspect of Video-ReID research. The investigation of temporal components, reallocation of prominent frames, and identification of significant frames is suggested through diverse approaches, including graph-based, attention mechanisms, transformers, and 3D convolutional neural networks. Multiple surveys offer a synthesis of those approaches [22-25].

Zhu, Lanyun, et al. [26] focus on selecting the most informative frames while minimizing computing cost. While Yang, Xi, et al. [27] concentrate on the development of robust spatial-temporal correlations in video sequences by manipulating low and high frequency components. Yu, Chenyang, et al. [9] introduce a text-free clip module that conceptualizes the sequence feature as a modifiable memory clip, integrating Temporal Memory Construction (TMC) and Memory Diffusion (MD).

On the other hand, Shutao Bai et al. [28] present the silhouette sequence as a biometric characteristic for pedestrians, encapsulating an individual's gait and height through frames. Graph-based research is initiated by Xian, Yuqiao, et al. [29] and Lu, Jiakuan, et al. [30]. Xian, Yuqiao, et al. [29] focus on rectifying the noisy labels for each tracklet using graph-based learning, thereafter transmitting the corrected labels through the trained model. While in [30] the authors concentrate on two main aspects: minimizing noise and improving temporal

connection among skeleton joints via dynamic hypergraphs.

2.2 Attention In Video ReID

Attention denotes the process of emphasizing notable features in a specific area while suppressing less relevant information. Attention mechanisms are utilized in image and video-based person ReID to identify significant regions, select important frames, and obtain distinctive representations. In video, attention can be leveraged across both spatial and temporal domains, as described in [31]. This method is employed to represent body parts in scenarios where they are concealed as explained in [32]. Furthermore, it is utilized to produce the most robust clip features through the application of weighted spatial-temporal features [33].

Chen, Guangyi, et al. [34] employ RNN to identify significant areas within frames, guided by appearance and optical flow streams. Shu, Xiujun, et al. [35] utilize the attention mechanism to identify prominent distinguishing features from frames, including shoes, hair, and bags, as well as aspects of appearance and color.

Wu, Lin, et al. [12] utilize Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to extract spatial features from each frame, subsequently concentrating on salient regions while ignoring non-salient areas through a combination of Siamese network and Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) directed by an attention mechanism. Zhang, Zhizheng, et al. [36], along with Randa et al. [11], examine the function of multi-granularity attention networks in extracting spatial and temporal features. Jiang, Xinyang, et al. [37] incorporated temporal attention across multiple salient levels to maintain the most essential frames while reducing frame redundancy, all without encountering inattentive loss.

2.3 Pose Features In ReID

In literature, heatmaps, optical flow, gait analysis, and skeletal detection are all closely representative motion features for person ReID. Miao, Jiayu, [38] employ heatmaps and keypoints as pose representative features for person ReID regarding occluded individuals. They integrate pose-based features with horizontally striped backbone features to accomplish their results.

Conversely, Zhang, Shanshan, [39] employs pose features in conjunction with attention mechanism for

detection tasks. In addition, Yuan, Chao, et al. [40] highlight the pose features role in aggregating neighboring features per identity.

Ahmad, Shafiqet, et al. [41] employ pose features for utilizing event-based cameras. While, Liu, Zhigang, et al. [42] employ the keypoints to address the occlusion issue. A confidence method is used across keypoints to obtain self-adaptive weights which enhance the features of non-occluded individuals while diminishing the weights of occluded individuals.

Miao, Yunqi, et al. [43] examine the pose features for visible-infrared ReID as supplementary attributes to enhance their architecture.

2.4 Pose Features In Video-ReID

Gao, Changxin, et al. in [17] employ pose features for spatial and temporal aggregation. Frames exhibiting analogue poses are combined to achieve temporal alignment, after which the components of each aligned pose are used for spatial feature extraction. On the other hand, Pan, Honghu, et al. [18] extract posture features for each frame and subsequently employed them to create a temporal graph for the video sequence.

A recurrent graph convolutional network is subsequently employed for the learning procedures. While, Yu, Hang, et al. [44]

Figure 2: The Proposed System.

exploit pose features to develop the Pose Aligned Feature Learning (PFL) module for unsupervised video person ReID. The PFL design leverages global characteristics to guide the classification of outlier samples.

Despite the remarkable progress achieved through attention mechanisms and pose-based representations in person Re-Identification (ReID), several research gaps remain evident in the current literature.

Existing approaches typically employ either attention mechanisms to emphasize salient regions or pose features to localize body parts. However, only a limited number of studies have explored a unified framework that effectively integrates pose-guided attention to enhance both spatial and temporal feature consistency. This limitation restricts the model's ability to jointly address occlusions, viewpoint variations, and motion inconsistency across video sequences.

Many prior studies integrate multiple features such as pose, appearance, and optical flow through simple concatenation or fusion. These methods mainly leverages global guidance and does not fully exploit fine-grained local pose relationships or temporal dependencies among frames.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY:

This section establishes the proposed framework, which comprises two fundamental components: (1) the spatial feature extraction module and (2) the temporal part-attention module. As illustrated in Figure 2, the input video frames are processed through a spatial feature extraction module operating at three distinct levels: GAF, MPF, and FPF. The fusion of these features is further presented for the TPM.

In the spatial feature extraction module, the input frames are divided into two distinct branches: the backbone branch and the pose estimation branch. ResNet50 serves as the backbone, which acquires pretrained features subsequently fed into two parallel modules: GAF and MPF. GAF is employed to extract global appearance aspects, while MPF employs the self-attention mechanism to determine attention scores for moderate horizontal part attention features. Whereas, the pose estimator branch is employed to extract posture heatmap features, referred to as FPF. The fusion of GAF, MPF, and FPF comprises the ultimate representation of spatial frame features, which are then passed to the TPM to capture inter-frame interdependence. In TPM, a temporal attention mechanism is employed to achieve feature aggregation across time. The enriched feature representations are then passed to

the classifier for the final person representation. Three loss functions are proposed to optimize the model: cross-entropy loss, hard triplet loss, and pose-guided loss.

3.1 Spatial feature extraction module:

In spatial feature extraction module; three level of distinct features are extracted. Each feature level works on different feature space to capture generalized and detailed representation for each frame.

a) The GAF Module

proposed to yield two distinct representations of X_{in} , where horizontal striding of the input features is provided as illustrated in Figure 3(b). X_{p1} denotes the division of the feature vector into $P1$ parts,

whereas X_{p2} signifies the division of the feature vector into $P2$ regions, whereas $P1=6$ and $P2=12$.

For Video-ReID system's accuracy enhancement, self-attention mechanism is employed to guide the global frame representation towards the most salient regions in different space features (X_{p1} and X_{p2}) in two branches. In the first branch, self-attention network is exploited for horizontally pooled features X_{p1} , and X_{p2} which are subsequently multiplied to obtain the attention scores X_{score} , as indicated in Eq.

b) The MPF Module

Figure 3: Spatial Feature Extraction Modules: GAF And MPF After Being Processed By The Resnet50 Backbone.

3.1.1 Global appearance features module:

As inspired by [11], ResNet50 is used as backbone to generate initial pretrained features where only three layers are utilized for initial feature extraction, X_{in} , which has the dimension $G \times I$. The resulting features X_{in} are then fed into GAF, as declared in Figure 3 (a), which applies convolution layers and batch normalization to generate frame-level global appearance features, X_{glob} , where $X_{glob} \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times W \times H}$, C is the number of channels, W is the frame width, H is the frame height.

3.1.2 Moderate part-attention feature module:

Correspondingly, the backbone features, X_{in} , are provided to the MPF to be distributed across two branches. Each branch decomposes the frame feature space into several parts, enabling the extraction of specific variable details according to the number of parts, thereby enhancing the representation of the person's spatial features. Two pooling layers are

1. The modified attention score is then applied to SoftMax, alongside with X_{in} to produce X_{k1} , Eq.2. Thus X_{k1} guides the global frame channel features X_{in} with the fine-grained weights, X_{score} .

$$X_{score} = X_{p1} \otimes X_{p2}, \quad (1)$$

$$X_{k1} = X_{in} + \text{softmax}(X_{in} \cdot X_{score}) \quad (2)$$

Likewise, the second branch employs self-attention network for the average pooling of X_{p1} , and X_{p2} . The resulting X_{p1_avg} and X_{p2_avg} are subsequently multiplied to calculate the attention scores X_{ave_score} , Eq.3. The modified attention score is then applied to SoftMax, alongside with X_{in} to produce X_{k2} , Eq.4. Thus X_{k2} similarly guides the global frame channel features X_{in} , with the fine-grained weights, X_{score} .

$$X_{ave_score} = X_{p1_avg} \otimes X_{p2_avg}, \quad (3)$$

$$X_{k2} = X_{in} + \text{softmax}(X_{in} \cdot X_{ave_score}) \quad (4)$$

Thus, the output X_{Mod} , is the integration of the following vectors: $X_{k1}, X_{k2}, X_{p1}, X_{p2}$.

3.1.3 Fine-grained pose-guided features module:

In this module, the input frames are processed by pose estimator, HRNet [45], to generate heatmaps of person of interest. Pose estimator extracts 18 Gaussian heatmaps for each person P representing the pose masks centered at (X_i, Y_i) , where i ranges from 1 to 18, and (X_i, Y_i) is one of the person's joints location. The suggested method employs bilinear interpolation to ensure that the heatmaps match the spatial dimensions of the backbone output, $G \times I$. The resulting vector is multiplied by the backbone output vector to provide sampled heatmaps, P'_i . The P'_i is further subjected to max pooling to obtain the final feature vectors, P_i^* [38]. Figure 4 clarifies the resulting joints heatmaps for a sample frame. Finally, the resultant spatial feature $X_{Spatial}$ is a composition of X_{glob} , X_{Mod} , and P_i^* .

Figure 4: The Original Frame And Corresponding Heatmaps Produced By Hrnet.

3.2 Temporal Part-Attention Module:

The cross-frame feature representation is generated by leveraging the spatial frame-level representation within the TPM. Specifically, the TPM applies temporal single head attention to each spatial feature component (X_{glob} , X_{Mod} , and P_i^*) to capture dependencies across frames [46]. Within this module, an attention mechanism computes frame-wise attention scores, following the application of two convolutional layers across the temporal dimension t . Convolutions are utilized to reduce the channel's dimension to a new dimension, B . This offers supplementary representation in the feature space. The attention score of sequential frames is derived by utilizing a SoftMax function as declared in Eq. 5

$$TPM = \text{softmax}(\text{conv}(\text{conv}(\text{feat}_t^x))), \quad (5)$$

3.3. Retrieval Module:

The retrieval module receives both query and gallery features to calculate the distance between them. The proposed framework utilizes three loss functions: the first is triplet loss (L_{tri}), which is commonly employed in person ReID [47], and the second is cross-entropy loss (L_{cross}) which measures the difference between the true and reidentified person. The third is the Pose loss, which pertains to the loss associated with each pose, (L_{pose}). Eq. 6 illustrates the total loss (L_{total}).

$$L_{total} = L_{tri} + L_{cross} + L_{pose} \quad (6)$$

4. IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS AND EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS:

The following subsections presents implementation details and performs ablation studies to assess performance. The proposed approach is evaluated utilizing two benchmark datasets: PRID2011 [48] and iLIDS-VID [49]. The components of the proposed methodology are evaluated initially and then compared to leading state of the art methodologies.

4.1. Implementation Details:

The proposed framework is implemented utilizing Pytorch framework on RTX4090 laptop with 16 GB of memory. The images have been resized to 384×192 then they are normalized utilizing the RGB mean and standard deviation. For MPF, the two parts branches are divided horizontally into 6 and 12 parts, respectively. The model is trained for 300 epochs, the input sequence length is 4 frames whereas the batch size is 8. The initial learning rate is 0.0003, *weight decay* is 5×10^{-4} , *gamma* is 0.1, *c* is 1024, and *c'* is 256. The number of *instances* (persons) in training batch is 2 for PRID2011, and 4 for iLIDS-VID dataset. The pose is estimated using HRNet, working under YOLO v3.

4.2 Datasets:

PRID 2011 Dataset. The PRID 2011 dataset consists of 385 identities captured using camera A and 749 identities captured using camera B. Among all individuals, 200 are recorded in both camera views. The length of each video sequence ranges from 5 to 675 frames. The main challenges of this

dataset are variations in lighting and alterations in human positions, Figure 5 (a) illustrates a sample of the dataset.

iLIDS-VID dataset. The iLIDS-VID dataset comprises 600 video segments featuring 300 participants. The length of video sequences ranges from 23 to 192 frames, with an average of 73 frames. This dataset is deemed more complex due to complicated backgrounds, occlusions, and similarities in apparel. Notably, with varying camera perspectives, the same individual could wear various clothes, Figure 5 (b) illustrates a sample of the dataset.

(A)

(b)

Figure 5: A) Sample Of PRID2011, B) Sample Of Ildis-VID Dataset, Credit Goes To [48] And [49].

4.3 Evaluation Metrics:

The performance evaluation is conducted by determining the ranking score between the gallery features and the inquiry features, with the ranking score arranged in descending order [50]. Two prevalent measures are utilized: Rank-n and Mean Average Precision (mAP).

Rank-n Accuracy:

Upon receiving a query image, the model generates a ranked list of identity matches from the gallery. A match is considered successful at rank-n if the correct identity appears within the top n retrieved results. Common evaluation ranks include rank-1, rank-5, rank-10, and rank-20, with rank-1 serving as

the strictest and most indicative measure of re-identification accuracy.

Mean Average Precision (mAP):

Mean Average Precision quantifies the overall retrieval accuracy by averaging the precision scores across all queries. It reflects the model's ability to consistently retrieve the correct identity from the gallery, accounting for both ranking order and relevance.

4.4 Experimental results:

This section presents a discussion of the experiments conducted to evaluate the proposed

system. The assessment begins with testing the system components, followed by subsequent experiments that integrate the FPF modules to examine their contribution to the overall performance.

Table 1 presents the results of the basic system, which comprises GAF, MPF, and TPM, conducted on the PRID2011 dataset on the first row. The results indicate that a mAP of 97.5% and a Rank-1 accuracy of 95.5% have been attained.

Whereas, the second row illustrates the benefit of utilizing the pose features by adding the FPF module where the mAP is increased by 1.4% and Rank-1 by 2.3%.

Alternatively, Table 2 presents the results of the base system, which comprises GAF, MPF, and TPM, over the iLIDS-VID dataset. The results indicate that a mAP of 92.8% and a Rank-1 accuracy of 88.4% have been attained (the first row). Whereas, the pose features (the FPF module) increase the mAP and Rank-1 by 1.2% by 3.4% respectively (the second row).

4.5 Comparison with state-of-the-art methods

Table 3 presents a comparison between the proposed system and the state-of-the-art approaches. The table presents several prior approaches together with their performance metrics, specifically mAP and Rank1 score, for the PRID2011 and iLIDS-VID datasets. The comparison also validates the foundational methodology of each method and the batch size employed during the training stage of each. The proposed strategy demonstrates greater performance despite using a small batch size compared to prior techniques. The table demonstrates that the suggested architecture achieves enhanced performance over most of the state-of-the-art approaches (11 of 15) across both datasets. In contrast, only four approaches

outperform ours Rank-1 over iLIDS-VID; namely: Lanyun Zhu [26], Bai [28], MTLA [49], and Cao [60] by 1.1%, 1.6%, 0.1% and 0.9% respectively.

Figure 6 illustrates various retrieval ranking outcomes based on the complexity of the query for iLIDS-VID. The query experiences occlusion due to other individuals or objects, clutter, and the presence of multiple humans in each frame. The retrieval results are regarding the IDs of individuals from the gallery, corresponding to the correct person, ranked from Rank-1 to Rank-5. The figure illustrates a rectangle surrounding each retrieved frame; a red rectangle signifies an incorrect match, whereas a green rectangle denotes a correct match.

The proposed pose-guided attention architecture achieves superior performance compared to most state-of-the-art methods—outperforming 11 of 15 approaches on both PRID2011 and iLIDS-VID datasets—demonstrating its effectiveness and robustness in handling occlusions and complex motion patterns even with smaller training batch sizes.

Table 1: System Components Results Over PRID2011.

Model/accuracy (%)	mAP	Rank-1	Rank-5	Rank-10	Rank-20
GAF + MPF + TPM	97.5	95.5	98.3	100	100
GAF + MPF + FPF + TPM	98.9	97.8	100	100	100

Table 2: System Components Results Over Ilids-VID.

Model/accuracy (%)	mAP	Rank-1	Rank-5	Rank-10	Rank-20
GAF + MPF+ TPM	92.8	88.4	98	99	99
GAF + MPF +FPF + TPM	94	91.8	98.6	98.6	99.3

5. CONCLUSION:

This research presents a novel structure for video-based person re-identification. Pose-guided features are integrated with attention-based feature learning to generate superior results. . The proposed framework bridges existing research gaps by unifying pose features and attention mechanisms within a multi-level spatial-temporal structure, enabling adaptive spatial feature fusion and temporal engagement. Incorporating three distinct spatial

features—global, moderate portion attention, and fine-grained features—enhances the outcomes. This level of combination facilitates the aggregation of many feature levels. The temporal attention module receives and processes all these combinations effectively to enhance reidentification outcomes. This hierarchical combination enhances spatial robustness against occlusions and viewpoint variations, while the temporal attention module adaptively models pose variation and motion dynamics across consecutive frames. Consequently,

TPM process the successive temporal information to achieve smooth and coherent temporal alignment. A group of distinct loss functions aids in minimizing the disparity between the query and gallery via the retrieval module. By addressing the limitations of existing approaches such as: pose–attention integration, static temporal modeling, and limited feature adaptability; the proposed method offers a comprehensive and interpretable solution for video-based person ReID. Experiments on two benchmark datasets indicate that the proposed design achieves high performance compared to the leading state of the art methodologies.

DATA AVAILABILITY:

The datasets analyzed during this research study are available on request.

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Table 3: Comparison Between The Proposed Approach And The State Of The Art Over PRID2011 And ILIDS-VID Datasets

Author	Approach	batch-size	PRID2011		ILIDS-VID	
			mAP	Rank 1	mAP	Rank 1
Snippet [56] (2018)	Temporal co-attention	32	-	93.0	-	85.4
STIM [58] (2019)	Refining Recurrent Unit	-	-	92.7	-	84.3
Li, Jianing [51] (2019)	3D convolution (M3D)	24	-	94.4	-	74.0
Subramaniam, et al. [57] (2019)	Attention (COSAM)	32	-	-	-	79.6
GLTR [59] (2019)	Self-attention	10	-	95.5	-	86.0
MGH [65] (2020)	Hypergraph Learning	32	-	94.8	-	85.6
Gu, Xinqian, et al. [53] (2020)	3D convolution (AP3D)	-	-	-	-	88.7
Attribute [36] (2020)	multi-granularity attention	64	-	95.9	-	88.6
MTV [13] (2020)	Graph based	16	-	96.0	-	90.9
AFA [64] (2020)	Adversarial Feature Augmentation	-	-	-	-	88.5
W. Song et al. [52] (2021)	LSTM	32	-	95.6	-	83.9
GRL [55] (2021)	Correlation Estimation	16	93.2	87.6	90.6	85.3
Bhuiyan et al. [63] (2022)	attention	32	-	-	-	88.3
Wang, Kan, et al. [61] (2023)	Attention (CSA-Net)	16	-	-	-	90.0
Cao, Chengzhi, et al. [60] (2023)	Spiking Neural Network	-	96.9	96.5	93.2	92.7
DCCT [62] (2023)	Transformer	16	-	96.8	-	91.7
Bai, Shutao [28] (2024)	Texture and silhouette	16	-	97.3	-	93.4
Liu et al. [8] (2024)	Transformer	32	-	96.4	-	91.3
Chen, Anming, et al. [49] (2024)	Encoders (MTLA)	16	-	97.0	-	91.9
Lanyun Zhu [26] (2025)	Transformer	-	-	96.4	-	92.9
Ours (2025)	Self-attention	8	98.9	97.8	94.0	91.8

Figure 6: Results For The Proposed System, The Query And The Retrieved Gallery Output For Ilids-VID Dataset.